

Rethinking the Successful Delivery of Complex NHS Hospital Projects: A Social Ontological Lens

Categories: 7. Social Value/ 9. Collaborative Working/ 6. Behaviour Change.

RESEARCH | INNOVATION |
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Problem

Since the 1960s, NHS hospital projects have consistently struggled to meet delivery expectations. Despite repeated reforms, in the UK, national bodies such as the National Audit Office and PAC continue to highlight persistent failures. The on-going Scottish Hospitals' Inquiry reinforces these conclusions.

“Current approaches have not delivered the number of new hospitals promised.” —Public Accounts Committee, (PAC) 2023. See also, (Love and Ika, 2022) for a global perspective.

Findings

7 linked research papers and over 33 NHS meeting analyses show how practical intelligibility emerges through situated sayings, doings, and relations. ASPVs make visible coordination and misalignment during uncertain decision points. O-P-G visualises social order as it unfolds, linking material arrangements, stakeholder actions, and teleoaffective structures. It reveals dynamic governance patterns and overlooked silences. Together, ASPVs and O-P-G demonstrate that NHS project delivery is enacted through evolving practice, not linear planning.

Innovation

This research introduces a novel **social ontological methodology** combining an innovative research method and a methodology:

- **Advanced Schatzkian Practice Vignettes (ASPVs):** A method of analysing situated sayings, doings, and relations in over 33 NHS project meetings. ASPVs make visible the contingent, affective, and often improvised practices through which project delivery during the critical front-end phase is enacted.
- **Open-Praxis-Graph (O-P-G):** As a transdisciplinary research methodology (TRM) that visualises how material arrangements, teleoaffective structures, and stakeholder practices interconnect over time. O-P-G as an TRM enables temporal and relational analysis of governance patterns, silences, and breakdowns. Together, ASPVs and O-P-G move beyond procedural and deterministic models by empirically tracing how social order emerges in the front end of NHS hospital projects. They offer a grounded method for understanding the *actuality* (Cicmil, et al., 2006) of the front-end phase project delivery as a dynamic, practice-based process.

Impact

This research contributes to society for socially valuable projects: A paradigm shift from procedural, managerial project planning to relational and ontological understanding. A methodology attuned to the lived complexity of NHS project governance. A framework for more transparent, participatory public infrastructure delivery in the context of today’s climate crisis.

Recent Alternative Scandinavian Approaches

Recent research by Larsen et al. (2021) and Kari-Pekka Tampio et al. (2023) provide valuable procedural insights into front-end hospital project governance.

This research extends their work by:

- Shifting from managerialism to **social ontology**, providing an original paradigm shift, that instead:
- Reveals underlying **social orders** that actually shapes project direction;
- Complements, such managerial perspectives with a **deeper ontological and empirical framing**, and that has been:
- Empirically substantiated via the award-winning NHS Dumfries & Galloway Hospital, amongst others: [Independent Architecture and Design Scotland Case Study](#)

References

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